

Table S8. Multivariate mixed effects logistic regression for *dhfr* and *dhps* gene mutations in pregnant women (pure mutants versus wild type/mixed)

Odds ratios (OR) with 95% CI and *p* values are presented (*p* values <0.05 in bold).

<i>dhfr</i> Fixed effect(s)	N51				C59				S108				triple <i>dhfr</i>			
	OR	[95% CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>
Age (10 years)	0.50	0.25	1.03	0.060	0.56	0.27	1.16	0.508	0.50	0.23	1.09	0.082	0.51	0.24	1.05	0.066
Gravidity	1.17	0.95	1.45	0.141	1.18	0.95	1.47	0.129	1.23	0.97	1.56	0.082	1.17	0.95	1.45	0.146
Season#	1.17	0.78	1.77	0.444	1.15	0.76	1.75	0.508	1.21	0.79	1.86	0.387	1.29	0.85	1.95	0.224
IPTp-SP doses	1.15	0.80	1.65	0.453	1.49	0.95	2.25	0.083	1.69	1.00	2.89	0.052	1.20	0.85	1.70	0.309
AL	0.82	0.53	1.28	0.385	0.97	0.59	1.58	0.896	0.83	0.49	1.41	0.499	0.87	0.56	1.34	0.523
Visit*	0.39	0.07	2.38	0.310	0.34	0.05	2.41	0.280	0.26	0.03	2.25	0.223	0.27	0.05	1.65	0.158
SeasonXvisit	2.38	0.89	6.34	0.083	2.61	0.93	7.33	0.069	2.97	0.93	9.47	0.066	1.91	0.71	5.13	0.201
-Visit* in high transmission season	0.94	0.18	4.76	0.938	0.88	0.15	5.25	0.893	0.78	0.11	5.67	0.808	0.52	0.10	2.61	0.429
-Season# in Del samples	2.79	1.14	6.80	0.024	3.00	1.17	7.72	0.023	3.59	1.17	10.99	0.025	2.46	1.00	6.05	0.049
AgeXvisit	0.79	0.22	2.87	0.722	1.18	0.30	4.68	0.810	1.08	0.25	4.78	0.915	0.54	0.15	1.98	0.356
-Age in Del samples	0.40	0.16	1.12	0.083	0.66	0.21	2.13	0.492	0.54	0.15	1.99	0.358	0.28	0.09	0.80	0.018
GravidityXvisit	1.29	0.86	1.94	0.211	1.13	0.73	1.73	0.589	1.19	0.73	1.92	0.484	1.42	0.95	2.12	0.090
-Gravidity in Del samples	1.52	1.07	2.14	0.018	1.33	0.92	1.93	0.134	1.46	0.95	2.26	0.088	1.66	1.18	2.33	0.004

<i>dhps</i> Fixed effect(s)	S436				A437			
	OR	[95% CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>
Age (10 years)	2.06	0.79	5.37	0.137	0.68	0.32	1.47	0.329
Gravidity	0.85	0.65	1.12	0.258	1.10	0.88	1.39	0.399
Season#	1.60	0.93	2.75	0.089	0.76	0.49	1.19	0.227
IPTp-SP doses	0.95	0.63	1.42	0.790	1.63	0.93	2.86	0.089
AL	0.94	0.57	1.56	0.821	0.67	0.40	1.12	0.125
Visit*	1.64	0.20	13.39	0.646	0.69	0.07	6.93	0.756
SeasonXvisit	0.90	0.27	3.05	0.867	1.79	0.46	6.90	0.398
-Visit* in high transmission season	1.47	0.21	10.21	0.694	1.24	0.15	10.15	0.840
-Season# in Del samples	1.44	0.47	4.41	0.522	1.36	0.38	4.87	0.635
AgeXvisit	0.72	0.15	3.55	0.686	0.66	0.13	3.47	0.626
-Age in Del samples	1.49	0.39	5.72	0.565	0.45	0.10	1.96	0.288
GravidityXvisit	1.06	0.66	1.70	0.814	1.08	0.64	1.80	0.780
-Gravidity in Del samples	0.90	0.60	1.35	0.621	1.19	0.75	1.88	0.464

Del = delivery; AL = artemether-lumefantrine therapy #dry season = 0, rainy season = 1; *ANC booking = 0, Delivery = 1; age centred at 25 years

